

Simulating Quantum Gate Distortion Effects with the Quantum Audio Python Package

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Abstract. *The quantum audio Python package is not only used to encode and decode a digital audio signal, but can also provide the foundation for creating distortion algorithms by adding gates in between the functions that encode and decode an audio signal. Various gates produce audibly different distortion effects. We mainly focus on four distinct gate combinations in this work and explore what value they bring artistically.*

Figure 1: Quantum Audio Distortion Pipeline where QPAM is a scheme in the quantum audio Python package

Figure 2: A Quantum Audio Pipeline. Instead of a real quantum device, a classical computer is simulating the quantum portion [10]

1 Introduction

The idea of combining fields as disparate as quantum computation [1, 2, 3, 4] and music technology may appear unconventional. However, considering how computer science and music technology have developed hand-in-hand since around the 1950s with the Ferranti Mark I, the intersection between the fields of computer science and music now grows and evolves beyond the classical domain. [5]

Whether it was the development of vinyl records, tapes, CDs, .mp3 files, or Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs), research on sound and audio signal processing has remained a relevant application of computation for over 70 years. In the 2020s, research has explored the subset of audio signal processing called quantum audio signal processing [6] which encodes a digital audio signal onto a circuit that is then in part executed on a quantum computer before it is decoded into results we can audibly observe.

Signals in quantum audio before 2020 [7, 8] are now commonly described using the terminology from the comprehensive literature on quantum audio which is chapter 10 of the 2022 quantum computer music book [9] entitled ‘Quantum Representations of Sound: From Mechanical Waves to Quantum Circuits’ [10].

The purpose of this work is to analyze what audible difference occurs to an audio signal when various quantum gates are applied before decoding the signal. This work builds off of the core functionalities of the quantum audio Python package by introducing distortion to the audio signal in the form of various quantum gates applied to a quantum state.

In this work, we find that in our simulated experiment quantum gates can audibly affect an audio signal with unitary operations on a quantum circuit. Determining the specific effects of different gates is a question that the proposed distortion effects provide an answer to.

We first describe the schemes that exist within the quantum audio Python package before diving into the pipeline of the Simulated Quantum Gate Distortion (SQGD) effects. Figures and code snippets will be utilized to attain detailed understanding of the inner-workings of the SQGD effects.

2 The Quantum Audio Python Package

The quantum audio Python package [11, 12] contains various schemes that map digital audio’s time to basis states and digital audio’s amplitude to probability amplitudes or basis states. How these mappings are performed or embedded depends entirely on the type of scheme, whether that be probabilistic-based or state-based.

Quantum Probabilistic Amplitude Modulation (QPAM) is a probabilistic-based method of quantum audio that maps digital audio’s time to basis states, but digital audio’s amplitude to a probability amplitude. For a deeper and more mathematical understanding of how QPAM handles mapping digital audio, QPAM is represented by:

$$|A_{\text{QPAM}}\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \alpha_i |i\rangle, \quad (1)$$

where $|A_{\text{QPAM}}\rangle$ is the initial digital audio signal, N is an arbitrary quantum audio of size N samples, α_i when modulus square is the complex probability amplitude representing digital audio's amplitude, and $|i\rangle$ is the time qubit representing digital audio's time.

3 Simulating Quantum Gate Distortion Effects

The SQGD effects add various quantum gates to a quantum circuit that has been encoded with the QPAM scheme of quantum audio. Any unitary quantum gate may be applied, with most of the initial experiments being done with the Pauli X, Y, Z gates, the Hadamard gate, or later on more circuits representing entanglement such as bell circuits or GHZ circuits.

This effect is not directly a part of the quantum audio Python package, but constitutes an extension of this package in the form of a Jupyter notebook. Since the quantum audio Python package utilizes IBM Quantum's [13] Software Development Kit (SDK) known as Qiskit, [14] all quantum audio experiments utilize Qiskit in some form.

The distortion effect pipeline of Fig. 1 is as follows:

1. Choose any digital audio file (.mp3 or .wav typically)
2. Encode digital audio's time and amplitude to QPAM
3. Apply a distortion algorithm in the form of quantum gates on a quantum circuit after the QPAM encoding
4. Decode the audio signal from the quantum circuit by either measuring the state or by extracting the probability distribution from the statevector simulation
5. Listen to the reconstructed audio signal and audibly observe any changes

Although the current implementation simulates a quantum computer, the distortion effect still occurs during the quantum processing portion of the pipeline, emulating a real quantum computer. To illustrate the effects, we consider the following example of a 1 second, 1 Hz sine wave of only eight samples.

Code 1: Calling QPAM

```
1 # Once a 1 second, 1 Hz sine wave with 8
  samples is created, call QPAM
2 qpam = quantumaudio.schemes.QPAM()
```

Following QPAM initialization, encode the sine wave using QPAM and decompose five times to examine the underlying unitary operations QPAM is performing. cf Fig. 3

Code 2: Encoding a Simple Sine Wave with QPAM

```
1 # Encode function, verbose 2 means seeing
  the underlying circuit
2 encoded_circuit = qpam.encode(sine_wave,
  measure=False, verbose=2)
```


Figure 3: QPAM Decomposed

Figure 4: Added X Gates to the Decomposed QPAM

```
3 # Optional deeper dive into underlying
  circuit
4 encoded_circuit.decompose().decompose().
  decompose().decompose().decompose().
  draw('mpl')
```

There are three qubits representing digital audio's time that have been mapped to eight basis states. Upon decomposition, QPAM applies a variety of unitary gates occurring before the distortion. After encoding, we apply a set of gates that are responsible for the distortion.

Code 3: Adding X Gates

```
1
2 # Adding X gates to all time qubits after
  encoding quantum audio scheme
3 from numpy import pi
4 for i in range(t_qubits):
5     encoded_circuit.x(i)
6
7 # Visualize the modified circuit
8 encoded_circuit.decompose().decompose().
  decompose().decompose().decompose().
  draw('mpl')
```

The distortion occurs at the application of the unitary gates after the QPAM encoding, which can be visualized in Fig. 4. When scaled to hundreds of thousands of sample points instead of eight, the X gate seems to audibly displace the signal while the H gate typically creates a higher pitched heavily noisy signal.

Instead of the X or H gate, this distortion effect allows for any other quantum gate to be applied. The examples in the next section contain the audio samples from these experiments using a variation of one and two qubit gates.

Since this was a tiny version of the SQGD effects, shot noise was hardly a factor in manipulating the signal, which allows for the code snippet below.

Code 4: Measuring and Decoding the Circuit

```
1
2 # Measure the circuit
3 qpam.measure(encoded_circuit)
4
5 # Decoding the encoded quantum circuit with
  high shot count
```

```
6 decoded_signal = qpam.decode(
    encoded_circuit, shots=1000000)
```

In practical experiments, shot noise has not been typically helpful, which becomes important to consider when scaling to inputs of audio that are 5-8+ seconds long. The examples do not have shot noise since the probability distribution from the statevector simulation was extracted to better represent the change from the distortion gates.

When it comes to using the SQGD effects, an ideal input audio file size would be an .mp3 or .wav file that is around 5 seconds, where any audio input is suitable. Most experiments were tested on music created by the first author.

4 Qualitative Analysis of the Results

Audio examples (including the four to five second input audio signal) of the SQGD effects were uploaded to an anonymous YouTube channel [15] with timestamps that will be referenced throughout this section. All gates mentioned are being applied to all time qubits unless specified otherwise.

At 0:04, the X gate qualitatively appears to displace the original audio signal, the harmonic content is preserved as the concert Ab Major Pentatonic sound still remains present harmonically. This same displacement of the audio signal happens with the Y gate at 0:15, however with the Z gate at around 0:06 the original audio remains largely unchanged.

At 0:11, we get a notable result with the $R_x(\frac{\pi}{2})$ gate that completely distorts the original audio signal to a point where you only audibly observe this distorted sound resembling early digital game audio effects. However, at 0:18 when the gate for the effect is $R_x(\frac{\pi}{4})$, similar distortion characteristics appear but with the original signal playing faintly in the background.

At 0:22, the H gate produces primarily noise with a high-pitched drone that sounds almost like a concert F5 but approximately a quarter-tone flat. This concert F drone in various octaves will be a theme when the H gate is involved. A notable result is at 0:31 where a $CNOT$ gate is applied only to the first two qubits where q_0 is the control and q_1 is the target, followed by an H gate on q_0 with no other gates on the other 16 qubits.

At 0:26, the $R_x(\frac{\pi}{6})$ gate produces a result similar to the $R_x(\frac{\pi}{4})$ gate except a repeated overlapping of the original signal is audibly present in the background. This repeated overlapping of the original audio signal can be audibly observed quite faintly in the background of the $R_x(\frac{\pi}{4})$ example but is amplified in the $R_x(\frac{\pi}{6})$ example. At 0:35, the audio demonstrates that the $R_x(\frac{\pi}{8})$ gate brings out more of the original audio signal while having the early digital game audio effects and repeated sound be more of the background.

At 0:40, we have a bell circuit only on the first two qubits, while the other 16 qubits are left untouched after the QPAM encoding. This result at 0:40 is a subtler version

Figure 5: Blues Trumpet Spectrogram

Figure 6: Bell Circuit Spectrogram

of the inverted bell circuit result that still has a strong presence of high-end in the output audio signal. At 0:44 the audio demonstrates our first GHZ circuit which is a linear GHZ circuit on only the first three qubits.

5 Quantitative Analysis of the Results

Four variations of the SQGD effects will be evaluated using the quantitative metrics of their spectrograms, Signal-to-Noise (SNR) ratios, cross-correlations, and spectral centroids. Regarding the choice of which four variations to analyze, the bell circuit, inverted bell circuit, CNOT, and GHZ circuit were the distortions used to create the musical composition "Q-Bars" which was presented at the 3rd ISQCMC, hence the focus on the data of those distortions.

In Fig. 5, which functions as our control signal with no distortion, we see between one and one and a half seconds that the signal peaks in intensity which is common for all four distortion variations. However, what is unique to this control signal is after two seconds we hardly get any signal above 8 kHz.

Regarding Fig. 6, the bell circuit variation of the SQGD visually reflects the control signal spectrogram more than

Figure 7: Inverted Bell Circuit Spectrogram

Figure 8: CNOT Spectrogram

Figure 9: GHZ Circuit Spectrogram

the other variations, especially when considering the lack of signal in the 8 kHz range after two seconds. The spectral centroid of the bell circuit variation is 1048.4 Hz when the control signal is 1790.4 Hz which implies the bell circuit has a darker timbre than the control signal. Notably, the bell circuit variation has the lowest value for its spectral centroid compared to the other three variations of the distortion effect.

With Fig. 7, which is the inverted bell circuit variation, there is more signal present around 10 kHz after two seconds than on the bell circuit variation and the original signal. While the only change between the bell circuit and inverted bell circuit variations was the order of gates, the inverted bell circuit variation had a cross-correlation of 0.9297 while the bell circuit variation had a cross-correlation of 0.9712. While the cross-correlation remained similar in values to the original signal, notably the spectral centroid of the inverted bell circuit was 1576.5 Hz which is a spectral centroid difference from the bell circuit of over 500 Hz. This result implies that the timbre of the inverted bell circuit was brighter than the timbre of the bell circuit, despite only the order of gates changing on the simulated quantum circuit after the QPAM encoding.

Fig. 8 shows a stronger signal between one and one and a half seconds similar to the control signal while also having the highest cross-correlation to the control signal with a value of 0.9725. This CNOT variation is an outlier among the other three SQGD variations because it has a SNR that is positive at 12.65 dB while the other three SQGD variations have SNR values all hovering around -6 dB. The spectral centroid is by far the highest with the CNOT variation being 2843.6 Hz which is over 1 kHz higher than the control signal's spectral centroid implying the CNOT variation is much brighter than the other signals that have been

analyzed.

Finally in Fig. 9, this GHZ circuit variation has signal in nearly all frequencies after two seconds except for the gap below 6 kHz. While the SNR is not unique for the GHZ circuit variation being -6.25 dB which is similar to both the bell circuit and the inverted bell circuit variations, the cross-correlation is 0.8194 which is the farthest from 1.0 out of all the analyzed SQGD effects.

For future quantitative analysis of SQGD effects, other metrics in signal processing to be considered are waveform comparisons, FFTs, frequency distributions, the mean squared error, the root mean square, and peak values.

6 Conclusion

We found that quantum gates can audibly distort an audio signal when encoded and decoded through the quantum audio Python package. Determining the specific effects of different gates on an audio signal can depend on how many gates are applied, where they are applied, and which gate is chosen to be added.

Since these experiments were done on simulators, with the audio examples extracting the probability distribution from the statevector simulation before measurement, there is plenty of room for future research to explore these experiments on simulated hardware and real devices.

The analysis demonstrates that even the order of the gates matters such as with the example of the bell circuit versus the inverted bell circuit that produced different results. There are many combinations of gates that can be applied for various musical and creative outputs depending on what the user wants.

It is also worth mentioning that alongside future quantum gate distortion effect research on real devices, having more empirical and scientific understanding as to why the output signals sound the way they do on simulators or real devices would be valuable information in the field of quantum audio signal processing.

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References

- [1] Michael A Nielsen and Isaac L Chuang. *Quantum Computation and Quantum Information*. Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [2] T G Wong. *Introduction to Classical and Quantum Computing*. Rooted Grove, Omaha, NE, 2022.
- [3] Andy Matuschak and Michael A Nielsen. Quantum computing for the very curious, 2019.
- [4] Scott Aaronson. *Quantum Computing Since Democritus*. Cambridge University Press, 2013.
- [5] Eduardo R Miranda, editor. *Advances In Quantum Computer Music*, volume 6. World Scientific, 2024.
- [6] Paulo Itaboraí. Towards quantum computing for audio and music expression, 2023.
- [7] J Wang. Qrda: Quantum representation of digital audio. *International Journal of Theoretical Physics*, 55:1622–1641, 2016.
- [8] K Chen, F Yan, A M Iliyasu, and J Zhao. Exploring the implementation of steganography protocols on quantum audio signals. *International Journal of Theoretical Physics*, 57:476–494, 2018.
- [9] Eduardo R Miranda. *Quantum Computer Music: Foundations, Methods and Advanced Concepts*. Springer, Cham, 2022.
- [10] Paulo V Itaboraí and Eduardo R Miranda. Quantum representations of sound: From mechanical waves to quantum circuits. In Eduardo R Miranda, editor, *Quantum Computer Music: Foundations, Methods and Advanced Concepts*, pages 223–274. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2022.
- [11] Paulo Vitor Itaboraí. Quantumaudio module, 2022. Software.
- [12] Moth Quantum and collaborators. Quantum audio, 2024.
- [13] IBM Quantum. Ibm quantum platform, 2025. Accessed: 7 February 2025.
- [14] Ali Javadi-Abhari, Matthew Treinish, Kevin Krsulich, Christopher J. Wood, Jake Lishman, Julien Gacon, Simon Martiel, Paul D. Nation, Lev S. Bishop, Andrew W. Cross, Blake R. Johnson, and Jay M. Gambetta. Quantum computing with Qiskit, 2024.
- [15] Simulated Quantum Gate Distortion. Simulated quantum gate distortion demo. YouTube, 2025. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mbWf_8bu3Nw.